
Enhancing localisation and dosimetry of radiation sources with machine learning techniques and a novel directional spectrometer

Master NAC thesis by

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Abstract

Today, the use of nuclear sources is growing alongside the nuclear sector. In workplaces with the presence of radiation fields, neutrons represent a serious hazards for workers, and the current state of neutron detection is relatively rudimentary. Some improvements have to be made, principally about detecting the particles direction and dose estimation. The development of machine learning techniques nowadays offers wide possibilities for their improvement. The goal of the nFacet project is therefore to develop an efficient novel dosimeter and spectrometer capable of localising radiation sources and decomposing neutron fields into multiple directional components using machine learning techniques. Composed of a modular detector, this system is capable of reconstructing both direction and fluence of any neutron and gamma source using two deep learning models: DeepCompass and nFluence.

In order to get information about the neutron detection performance of the newly developed system of the project, nFacet M2, the present work made Geant4 data simulations to train the models with the new system. Measurements were taken in the field to do a finetuning of the directionality model. Some geometry modifications in the simulation were also realised to verify the performance of the system with less detector modules, and eventually create a lighter version in the future.

Contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Current state-of-the-art of neutron radiations dosimetry	6
2.1	What is dosimetry?	6
2.2	Evolution of the neutron dosimetry	8
3	nFacet 3D: A Promising Directional Spectrometer	11
3.1	Detector description and detection principle	11
3.2	nFacet M1	11
3.3	nFacet M2	12
3.4	Machine Learning Methods	13
4	Simulations and generation of the training datasets	14
4.1	Modifications of the detector geometries	14
4.2	Source addition	17
4.2.1	New neutron spectra	17
4.2.2	Simulations of thermal sources: FRUIT's formulae	18
5	Reconstruction of the direction of neutrons	20
5.1	Dataset creation and predictions' visualisation	20
5.2	Machine learning results: 4 boxes system	21
5.3	Finetuning using an AmBe source	23
5.4	Machine learning results: 2 boxes system	25
6	Fluence reconstruction for dose estimation	27
6.1	Data generation	27
6.2	Fluence reconstruction results	28
7	Conclusion	29
A	Overview of the geometries used to calculate fluence-to-dose conversion coefficients	33
B	4 boxes system angular error of the positions predicted by the DeepCompass model for 4 different sources	34
B.1	^{252}Cf thermalised using FRUIT's formulae	34
B.2	$^{241}\text{AmLi}$	35
B.3	PuO_2	36
B.4	$^{241}\text{AmBe}$	37
C	Losses comparisons of the finetuning trainings	38
D	2 boxes system angular error of the positions predicted by the DeepCompass model for 8 different sources	39
D.1	$^{241}\text{AmLi}$	39
D.2	^{238}U	40

D.3	D ₂ O-moderated ²⁵² Cf	41
D.4	PuO ₂	42
D.5	PuMetal	43
D.6	PuBe	44
D.7	²⁴¹ AmB	45
D.8	²⁴¹ AmBe	46
E	Calculation of the cone positions for dose estimation	47
F	Fluence reconstruction of 7 different sources	48
F.1	²⁵² Cf	48
F.2	²⁴¹ AmLi	49
F.3	²⁴¹ AmB	50
F.4	²³⁸ U	51
F.5	PuBe	52
F.6	PuO ₂	53
F.7	PuMetal	54
G	Neutron capture similarity of the ²⁵²Cf and ²⁴¹AmBe sources	55

1. Introduction

At the nuclear era, the need for nuclear power is growing alongside the demand for electricity. The latest report from the *International Energy Agency (IEA)* [1] let us know that nuclear power produces under 10% of global generation, being the second largest source of low emissions electricity today after hydropower. In 2023, more than 410 reactors were in operation in over 30 countries and energy generated from nuclear plants are set to reach a new peak in 2025. In France for example, about 70% of the electricity is derived from nuclear energy with 17% coming from recycled nuclear fuel, showing how important nuclear energy is today [2].

The use of radiation in medical fields has also become a routine today for everyone. Up to 50% of the radiation exposure of the population can be attributed to medical sources in countries with a developed clinical sector [3], most of it coming from X-Rays and Computed Tomography scan technology to diagnose injuries and disease.

In ionising environments, external dosimetry is absolutely necessary for the well-being of workers, mainly concerning gamma rays and neutron sources which are the biggest dose-drivers. Though the current state of gamma-rays dosimetry is at a good advancement, there's still a lot to do to improve the one of neutron radiations as they're more difficult to detect. The need for an improvement in radiations dosimetry is then real, and is the reason of the development of the nFacet project, which was initially developed for neutron dosimetry using directionality.

As of today, few neutron detection systems are capable of giving the direction of a source because most of them need a moderator in order to thermalise the neutrons to facilitate their detection. The problem is that in these moderators the neutrons will give some of their kinetic energy and change directions after a nuclear interaction like a scatter, a capture or a fission, making the spatial localisation of the source more difficult. And looking for the direction from which the neutrons come from can be seriously useful for source detection, principally when we don't know from where the radiations are coming. The use of directionality can be used in various fields like area monitoring, homeland security, passive package inspection or even for nuclear verification treaties, giving both a gain in time and money. A device capable of localising a source that way would then sign a significant advancement in external neutron dosimetry, and this is indeed the objective of the nFacet 3D system. Also being a gamma and muon detector, its primary goal is to revolutionise neutron detection, first for dosimetry and then for eventual security applications.

2. Current state-of-the-art of neutron radiations dosimetry

2.1 What is dosimetry?

To begin with and to put it simple, dosimetry is the scientific method and measurement of the absorbed dose of ionising radiation. It is the measurement of the dose or energy received by a radiation field to quantify stochastic health risks. It plays a major role in the question of workers protection in a various range of industries going from the obvious nuclear sector to the medical field by passing by any industrial environment with radiative fields. Radiation dosimetry basically reads and tracks ionising radiation by using the deposited energy depending on the particle, i.e. the energy breaking electrons from atoms and molecules. Ionisation can have both natural sources such as cosmic rays or Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material (NORM) like the uranium chain, the thorium chain or potassium-40, or can come from human-made ones like X-rays.

There are 5 types of ionising radiations:

1. Alpha particles, that can be stopped with a simple sheet of paper because of their charge and their mass.
2. Beta particles, that can be stopped directly by the skin.
3. X-rays, known to be able to pass through organic matter. They however struggle with materials made with elements with a high atomic number Z because of the increase in photoelectric absorptions.
4. Gamma rays, with an even greater penetration properties. They generally can be stopped with lead, like all of the radiations above.
5. Neutrons, the most penetrative one among the five, that even lead can't really stop, they need to be moderated by elements rich in hydrogen.

A received dose of ionising radiation can be measured with a dosimeter. To measure the ambient dose, we rather use a radiometer. Both of them use different measurable quantities to estimate the absorbed dose, starting by the fluence, noted Φ , which represents the number of particles or ionising radiations that has traversed the material per unit area, in cm^{-2} . Another one is also crucial for dosimetry: the absorbed dose. It is basically a non-stochastic quantity which consists in a simple mass energy deposit that can be applied to both indirectly and directly ionising radiations. For indirectly ionising radiations, the energy is transmitted in 2 steps: indirectly ionising radiation to secondary charged particles and secondary charged particles to the medium, resulting in the mass energy deposit, with a loss of energy in the form of radiation losses like a bremsstrahlung or by an annihilation in flight [4]. The absorbed dose can then be defined as the mean energy transmitted by ionising radiations to matter of mass m in a finite volume V : $D = \frac{d\bar{\epsilon}}{dm}$. This physical quantity is measured in Gray (Gy, or J/kg), the unit of ionising radiation dose in the International System of Units.

Using these physical quantities, protective quantities are today defined by the *International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP)*. Between them, the most important ones for us here are the

equivalent dose and the effective dose. They're both defined in the ICRP Publication 74 [5]. As radiations affects health differently, and organs have different sensitivities, some factors are necessary to take into account these differences. In order to define the equivalent dose H , a radiation weighting factor w_R is then applied to the absorbed dose D to consider how much each type of radiation affect health, such that

$$H_T = w_R D_{T,R} \quad (1)$$

where T is the tissue or the organ considered and R the radiation type [4]. **Table 1** lists the range of values for this factor from the current in force Euratom Council publication [6] with the corresponding radiation type. It can be noted that in function of the energy of the neutrons the factor changes. With this factor, the unit considered for the equivalent dose isn't the Gray anymore but the Sievert (Sv).

Radiation type and energy	Radiation weighting factor w_R
Photons, all energies	1
Electrons and muons, all energies	1
Protons and charged pions, all energies	2
Alpha particles, fission fragments, heavy nuclei	20
Neutrons, $E_n < 1$ MeV	$2.5 + 18.2e^{-[\ln(E_n)]^2/6}$ (2.5 to 20.7)
Neutrons, $1 \text{ MeV} \leq E_n \leq 50 \text{ MeV}$	$5.0 + 17.0e^{-[\ln(2 \cdot E_n)]^2/6}$ (20.7 to 5.5)
Neutrons, $E_n > 50 \text{ MeV}$	$2.5 + 3.25e^{-[\ln(0.04 \cdot E_n)]^2/6}$ (5.5 to 2.5)

Table 1: Radiation weighting factor values depending on the radiation type [6]

To consider afterwards each organ sensitivity, a tissue weighting factor w_T is also defined. The effective dose is then defined, in Sv, as the summation of tissue equivalent doses each multiplied by the appropriate tissue weighting factor, such that it correlates well with all stochastic effects combined:

$$E = \sum w_T H_T = \sum_T w_T \sum_R w_R D_{T,R} \quad [4]. \quad (2)$$

A table of the tissue weighting factors can also be found in the same Euratom Council publication as before [6].

The only problem of the effective dose itself is that it is only a calculated value, it isn't directly measurable. For this reason, the *International Commission on Radiation Units and Measurements (ICRU)* defines specific operational quantities. Between these quantities, two of them are of interest: the ambient dose equivalent $H^*(d)$, used by radiameters, and the personal dose equivalent $H_p(d)$ for individual monitoring, used by dosimeters. They're defined in the ICRU report 57 [7], like in the ICRP report cited before. The ambient dose equivalent corresponds to the dose equivalent at a point in a radiation field that would be produced by the corresponding expanded field for a given direction in a sphere of 30 cm of soft human tissue, also called "ICRU sphere", at an appropriated depth d of generally 10mm [8, 9]. In the other hand, the personal dose equivalent consider a depth d at a designated point on the human body, i.e. the point where should be the dosimeter, and exposure from all directions [10, 11]. It is important to note that these quantities estimate the effective dose E . They're also measured in Sv and are both used to estimate the dose absorbed and assess the risks. A good summary of all these dose quantities can be found in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Summary of the link between the different dose quantities used for external radiological protection.

2.2 Evolution of the neutron dosimetry

Neutron radiations are more difficult to detect than other types of radiations. They're neutral particles so they don't interact electromagnetically with matter. This property makes them harder to detect because we then need a nuclear interaction to stop them, and they tend to scatter a lot with the environment, principally around water sources. In addition to that, the energy of neutrons created can also vary in a very wide order of magnitudes in energy in workplaces. In nuclear fission reactors for example, it can go from thermal neutrons, at around 0.025 eV, to fast neutrons that can reach energies up to 1-20 MeV.

Another limiting point for detectors is the radiation weighting factor w_R used for equivalent doses. Indeed, measuring the energy of neutrons is already quite difficult, and the radiation weighting factor is an energy-dependent function for neutron radiations as it can be seen in **Table 1**.

Neutron detection is therefore a real challenge, and an improvement in its dosimetry is necessary principally for the safety of workers in the nuclear industry or in neutron producing facilities as fast neutrons is a serious environmental hazard for them. They're indeed known to be able to produce ionisation inside the tissues of the body with consequent release of free radicles, causing structural damage to chromosomes and rupture of large protein molecules [12].

For energy measurements, the standard in neutron spectrometry is without a doubt the Bonner sphere spectrometer (BSS), a device capable of determining the energy spectrum of a neutron flux. It basically consists in using a thermal neutron detector, usually a ${}^6\text{Li}(\text{Eu})$ or a ${}^3\text{He}$ scintillator nowadays, surrounded by several polyethylene spheres of various sizes capable of moderating neutrons of higher energies depending on the size of the sphere. They generally have an energy range up to 20 MeV, but recent studies are trying to improve their energy range using lead shells for examples [13]. According to a 2006 CERN report, BSS have peaks of absolute neutron fluence response between 1 and 3.5 cm^2 de-

pending on their size and then the range of neutron energy detected. As expected the bigger ones tend to react more to high-energy neutrons [14]. But despite their efficiency, Bonner spheres require a good amount of time to perform measurements. The measurements are quite long enough by themselves but in addition the fluence have to be deconvolved using a slow algorithm with calculation hypothesis, and thus cannot be used as a personal dosimeter or as a radiameter.

For dose measurements, the reference today is the Berthold LB 6411 neutron dose rate probe [15]. According to a Berthold's datasheet, it consists of a polyethylene moderator sphere with a composite ^3He recoil proton counter tube at its center. The system can be easily operated as a portable measuring device using an universal monitor (UMo II) LB 134, or it can be used as a stationary system with the LB 115 data logger. 2 different versions are available: The LB 6411 we just talked about and the LB 6411-Pb version for high-energy applications. The datasheet also provides us that the LB 6411 weights 9.2 kg, has a measuring range of 30 nSv/h to 100 mSv/h for a neutron energy range going from thermal neutrons (so around 0 eV) to 20 MeV. They also display a ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ response of 2.83 counts per nSv relative to an unmoderated ^{252}Cf spectrum. But the real problem of this system is first that it can't measure the energies of the neutrons it detects, it is only capable of detecting their presence once they're stopped in its moderator. Secondly, it is not capable of estimating the directions from where the neutrons come from. And being able to do it is not only a gain in time when looking for a radioactive source, but also a gain in money, which is why other detectors are trying to develop this aspect.

Created more recently, the DIAMON (Direction-aware Isotropic and Active neutron MONitor) detector developed by RAYLAB s.r.l., a private company spin-off of the Polytechnic University of Milan (*Politecnico di Milano*), is at the moment a promising neutron detector available in the market, capable of directionality. Being not as slow as a Bonner Sphere and completely portable like the Berthold LB 6411, it is made of a polyhedral moderator body made of high-density polyethylene with a matrix of neutron sensors made by combining semiconductor devices with a ^6LiF -based radiator [16]. According to a Raylab's datasheet [17], DIAMON weighs around 6.0 kg and 8.5 kg, depending on either we use the low energy or the high energy version, so lighter than the LB 6411. It also has an ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ rate measuring range going from 10 nSv/h to 100 mSv/h and a response of 1.03 counts per nSv relative to an AmBe spectrum. Though it has a lower response than the Berthold LB 6411 probe, it has a better measuring range and is capable of directionality. DIAMON shows then itself to be a promising easy-to-transport instrument in neutron localisation, capable of real-time neutron spectrometry, something the LB 6411 can't do, and even proposing a wider ambient dose equivalent rate measuring range.

Other competitors also exist like the Fuji NSN3 radiameter, even lighter than the DIAMON detector, only 3.0 kg, but with a shorter neutron energy range, going up to 15 MeV [18]. However these detectors still encounter some serious issues. Firstly, they're built to only give the users the measurement of the ambient dose equivalent, they can't measure directly the energy like a spectrometer which means that whenever a modification in the conversion coefficients in the standards is made, they have to be re-certified or worse, redesigned and the users have to buy a new system. And there are good reasons to think that the standard will change in the upcoming years as the neutron fluence-to-dose conversion coefficients defined in ICRP-74 [5] for ambient dose equivalent are known to overestimate the ones of the effective dose for the right and left lateral geometries, and can be improved for the other geometries, as it can be seen in **Figure 2**. A schematic of the geometries cited before is supplied in **Appendix A**.

Figure 2: Fluence-to-dose conversion coefficients compared to the ambient dose equivalent quantity defined by ICRP report 74, adapted from Nicholas Reed thesis [5, 19]. AP, PA, LLAT and RLAT refer to radiation incident from the front (Antero-Posterior), back (Postero-Anterior), left lateral and right lateral directions. The ROT geometry assumes a person slowly rotating in a unidirectional applied field and the ISO geometry assumes an isotropic field.

One of the most recent ICRU report, ICRU-95 [20], already suggests significant changes in the conversion coefficients. That is the reason why being able to have a hand on measured physical quantities directly, i.e. the fluence here, is better as the operational quantities can be calculated afterwards, and any change in the standards will just result in an update in the tables. Finally, with their method of detection they still can't decompose correctly the neutron field into multiple directional components. But the use of machine learning techniques for detection can change everything.

Since the early 2000's, it is important to note that the use of neural networks to estimate neutron spectra was already considered, starting from using Bonner Sphere spectrometers [21] to bare ⁶Li detectors [22], but no radiameter as efficient as the ones cited above has yet ever tried to couple their detection process with machine learning techniques. If the past few years have shown us something, it is indeed how powerful machine learning can be if used efficiently. And they can estimate the energy of the neutrons detected, which means the energy is directly measurable. This is then the goal of the nFacet project: to create an easily updatable, efficient and transportable radiameter capable of localising radiation sources and decomposing neutron fields, or even gamma-neutron fields, into multiple directional components using machine learning techniques.

3. nFacet 3D: A Promising Directional Spectrometer

nFacet is one of the most promising recently developed spectrometers capable of detecting at the same time gamma rays, neutrons and muons. The conception of this detector emerges from a prototype for the SoLid (Search for oscillations with a Lithium-6 detector) experiment, dedicated to high precision reactor neutrino measurements at very short distances from a reactor core [23]. The goal of this section is then to describe this promising spectrometer, explain its detection principle and how it has evolved through time.

3.1 Detector description and detection principle

The detector is basically made of 64 ELJEN Technology EJ-200 $5 \times 5 \times 5$ cm³ polyvinyl-toluene (PVT) based plastic scintillators [24], each one of them associated with a ⁶LiF:ZnS(Ag) sheet of 250 μm from Scintacor [25]. The association of both a PVT scintillator and a ⁶LiF:ZnS(Ag) sheet is what we call in the system a "cube". They're then all assembled in planes of 4×4 by module, the modules are stacked in a typical 4x4x4 configuration, resulting in 64 cubes hold together by an aluminum frame and optically separated with Tyvek sheets.

These PVT scintillators were selected first because any charged particles going through will produce scintillation photons with a decay time of 2 ns with a high light-yield of 10k photons/MeV with electrons, allowing us to detect both gamma rays and muons. They were also selected because of their neutron moderation properties, as they're rich in hydrogen, reducing the energy of each neutron to the thermal range and then facilitating the neutron capture with the ⁶Li neutron screens following the ⁶Li(n,α) reaction:

Most of the neutrons moderated are then captured with a deposited energy of 4.78 MeV. Of course neutrons can also be captured by the screens even without being in the thermal range, but as the energy grows, the cross-section of the screens lowers, making high-energy neutrons much more difficult to detect unless moderated.

The segmentation in cubes has been made in order to get "voxels" (volume pixels) and get an idea of the interaction position. The choice of a 5 cm cube is related to the neutron moderation length, and 4 cubes were chosen because they are effective in moderating neutrons of several tens of MeV [19].

3.2 nFacet M1

The first version of the detector, the nFacet Mark 1, see **Figure 3a**, was first created as a prototype for the SoLid experiment. Though it was optimised for nuclear security application, this system wasn't made to be sold afterwards, some improvements were then necessary starting by reducing its weight, 16 kg. This system also used 3 LiF:ZnS(Ag) sheets per PVT scintillators to maximise the neutron detection efficiency for nuclear security applications, where a sensitivity to low rates is decisive.

(a) nFacet M1, the first version of the nFacet system

(b) nFacet M2, current system

Figure 3: Evolution of the nFacet systems

3.3 nFacet M2

The nFacet Mark 2 system, see **Figure 3b**, was then created as an enhancement of the M1 model: no monolithic design but a stack of 4 3D-printed carbon fiber cases with 16 cubes and 2 analogue boards mounting 4 Silicon PhotoMultipliers (SiPM) each, lighter and easier to transport with a grip, works with its portable battery and its own tablet microcomputer. It was made modular for it to be more like usual radimeters and eventually to try it out with less boxes in order to create, someday, an even lighter version like modern radimeters, for example like the Fuji NSN3 cited before which only weights 3 kg. A lot of improvements were also made in the electronics and their performance. As this new model focus more on dose measurements than nuclear security applications, the number of LiF:ZnS(Ag) sheets per PVT scintillators was reduced to one, as such sensitivity wasn't necessary anymore and considering the cost of each Li screens for a single system. The new model becomes then more efficient though it is more difficult to produce. A comparative table of the two systems can be seen on **Table 2**.

	nFacet Mark 1	nFacet Mark 2
System dimensions	$25 \times 25 \times 27 \text{ cm}^3$	$25 \times 25 \times 21 \text{ cm}^3$
System weight	16 kg	15 kg assembled, 1.7 kg/box
Number of cubes	64	4×16
Field of view	4π	
Neutron energy range (NS mode)	Thermal – 20 MeV	
Fast Neutrons mode energy range (ES mode)	0.5 – 50 MeV	
Neutron efficiency (NS/ES modes)	0.2–0.4 / 0.15	0.1–0.2 / 0.8
Gamma-ray energy range (ES Mode)	150 keV - 4 MeV	
Gamma-ray energy resolution	$\sim 20\%$ at 1 MeV	
Trigger modes	NS, ES	NS, ES, random, pre-scaling, coinc.
Waveform Digitisation	33 MS/s	65 MS/s
Interface / Connection	ETH, Python DAQ	ETH/Wi-Fi with the Raspberry PI, C++ DAQ on muPC
Power	5V power cable or power bank	7W to 5V

Table 2: Comparison nFacet M1 vs nFacet M2 on different aspects

3.4 Machine Learning Methods

To reconstruct the fluence, the direction and the dose we will use methods based on neural networks. Then, two different models come with the nFacet system:

- The DeepCompass model, for gamma and neutron directionality.
- The nFluence model, trained for decomposing neutron fields' fluence in multiple components (thermal, epithermal and fast neutrons).

Both will be trained using supervised learning, which means we will use labelled datasets to train the algorithms to predict certain outcomes and recognise patterns in positions or dose components. Although the DeepCompass model has been used up until now on gamma rays data, it hasn't been yet tested on neutron fields. The nFluence model as for it was developed by Nicholas Reed for the M1 system [19] and was updated to be used for the M2 system, but no simulations were done yet with it, thus giving the whole objective of this project: generate data and see how the models work with new neutron data with the nFacet M2 system.

4. Simulations and generation of the training datasets

Before working on the system, Geant4 simulations are necessary to know what to expect from the results on the field. As we do supervised training sessions, generating data is necessary in order to train our models. Most of the work involves generating these data, as we cannot train our model solely from in-field measurements due to the time required to take them. So we pre-train our models using simulating data and finetune them on real data if possible, it's not possible for nFluence for example. But before doing these simulations, some modifications had to be made about what was done before in the simulations concerning some bugs, the correction of the ${}^6\text{Li}$ scintillator placement, adding the interactions' time stamp and some geometry modifications.

4.1 Modifications of the detector geometries

(a) Spatial orientation of the boxes for the simulations

(b) ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS(Ag)}$ sheets placement (the carbon boxes and the aluminium frame were hidden here)

Figure 4: Geometry of the system in the simulations

For the simulations to work, a gdml (geometry description markup language) file representing the system was created by Eliot Martin during his master's internship back in 2023 [26]. An important characteristic of the system is its asymmetry due to the placement of the ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS(Ag)}$ sheets under the PVT scintillators (**Figure 4b**): the last cubes will then always capture more thermal and less fast neutrons than the others as the fast neutrons coming directly to the ${}^6\text{Li}$ sheets (in $-z$) thus exposed won't be moderated and will just pass through it, at the opposite the thermal ones will get straightly captured. This asymmetry is directly visible on heatmaps when generating neutron data, but the ${}^6\text{Li}$ screens were not placed correctly in the gdml file, they were placed above instead of below the PVT

scintillators, inverting the asymmetry of the detector. A correction has then been made and can be observed easily with the heatmaps in **Figure 5**. Note that following the axes, the cubes are numbered from 0 to 3.

Figure 5: Heatmaps of the ^{252}Cf source (fast neutrons) at $x = 0$, $y = 0$, $z = 1$ m from the center of the detector. The frame was temporarily removed to add visibility on the effect.

In order to perform studies of material reduction, 3 other geometry files were created of the system with 48, 32 and 16 cubes by removing a box from the top to the bottom respectively. The 1 box system (with 16 cubes) is expected to be inefficient for fast neutrons capture because of its exposed ^6Li screens that have no moderation on a side as already explained before, and also because of its lack of surface, reducing considerably the fluence on the sides. Using some simulations with the source placed in the z direction ($+z$ and $-z$) and with a constant fluence, **Figure 6** shows indeed what we were expecting, but also that the 2 boxes geometry doesn't lose that much in neutron counts and can be studied at the same time as the 4 boxes standard system.

Figure 6: Number of boxes comparison for neutron capture (capture = 0 or 1 when a neutron is captured in a $^6\text{LiF}:\text{ZnS}(\text{Ag})$ screen)

For a better overview of the 4 systems, their neutron capture efficiency was calculated following x , $+z$ and $-z$ depending on the energy of the neutrons, as it can be seen in the **Figures 7a, 7b and 7c**. Following x , the particles arrive parallel to the lithium sheets and the efficiency of the system for thermal neutrons can go up to 25% for the 4 boxes system. It then decreases with the neutron energy, with a slight peak for fast neutrons at 1 MeV of 15% of efficiency. However following $+z$ and $-z$ a huge difference can be seen in the efficiency of the detector, which can be explained by the asymmetry of the system.

Neutron capture efficiency (following x) depending on the energy for a 4, 3, 2 and 1 box system

(a) Following x

Neutron capture efficiency (following z) depending on the energy for a 4, 3, 2 and 1 box system

(b) Following $+z$

Neutron capture efficiency (following $-z$) depending on the energy for a 4, 3, 2 and 1 box system

(c) Following $-z$

Figure 7: Capture efficiency of the 4 systems depending on the energy

As we can see on **Figure 8**, the detector shows a really low efficiency for neutron capture following $+z$, especially for thermal neutrons. This is because of the placement of the lithium screens. Indeed,

following $+z$ the first thing the particles will encounter when hitting the detector are the PVT scintillators. For fast neutrons, the PVTs will provide a moderation and help for capture afterwards. However for neutrons with lower energies, the hydrogen will just diffuse the neutrons and prevent them from being captured. At the opposite, following $-z$, the thermal neutrons will first encounter the lithium screens placed underneath and will get captured right off the bat. Unmoderated fast neutrons will pass through but will still eventually be captured after being moderated, joining the capture efficiency of the system for fast neutrons following $+z$. These efficiencies were tested and confirmed experimentally.

Figure 8: Comparison of the capture efficiency of the 4 systems depending on the energy following $+z$ and $-z$

4.2 Source addition

In order to generate data, energy spectra of different known neutron sources were added by hand in our macros' generation program. Some sources were already present: a ^{252}Cf pure source, a D_2O -moderated ^{252}Cf source, an AmBe source and an AmB source all extracted from the ISO 8529-1:2001 about Reference neutron radiations (Part 1) [27], with also an AmLi source calculated in Tagziria's paper about *The ideal neutron energy spectrum of $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ sources* [28]. Although ^{252}Cf and $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ are the most common sources, we still lacked diversity in the sources to train our models, particularly with regard to thermal neutron sources. That is why we had to look for more examples to generate.

4.2.1 New neutron spectra

Using a technical report from the International Atomic Energy Agency, we managed to find a compendium of new neutron spectra [29]. The first one we decided to add was the PuBe, an α -neutron source. The isotope used in our source isn't specified, it might even be a mix of multiple isotopes, but the 238 and the 239 isotopes were generally used in the past for dosimeters and instrument calibrations. They got replaced now by $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ sources to prevent the proliferation of plutonium. Because of its significant presence in ionising environments, ^{238}U was also a source of choice for our work. We also decided to take two other plutonium sources: the plutonium dioxide (PuO_2), notably known as a heat source for space programs like NASA's radioisotope power system [30, 31], or present in mixed oxide fuels (MOX) used in light-water reactors, and the plutonium metal (PuMetal) mainly found on weapons. In order to verify the spectra we added, we performed some simulations of the sources and compared the energy spectra generated for each source to the original energy spectra from the document with a scaling factor to make them match. The comparisons of the 4 sources spectra can be seen

in **Figure 9**. Note that the spectra generated after our simulations depend on the detection efficiency of the detector as we reconstruct the spectra from the energy created with each particle detected by the system. This explains why the literature’s spectra always prevail for higher energies, our simulated spectra have less data on faster neutrons as they’re harder to detect. By putting the x-axis in log, a serious loss in thermal neutrons can be observed after simulation, especially for the ^{238}U and PuO_2 spectra, that is probably due to their low probability.

Figure 9: Energy spectrum of each new source after simulation, position $(x = 0, y = 0, z = 1 \text{ m})$, x-axis in log, compared to literature

4.2.2 Simulations of thermal sources: FRUIT’s formulae

The only problem we still had was the fact that we only had spectra of sources generating mostly fast neutrons, and finding a source capable of only generating thermal neutrons is unfortunately not possible, unless maybe looking for a moderated source which spectrum will be hard to find, and also considering the fact that the spectrum will depend on the moderator, its shape, its composition and on the source itself. Simulating thermal sources is important to train our models, particularly for the nFluence model in order to be able to decompose a simulated neutron field, using different sources, into multiple components. It is also important when we don’t know where the fast neutron source is placed as the environment will generally moderate the source, with the presence of water or hydrogen, meaning that most of the time what the detector will measure is thermal and epithermal neutrons.

In order to overcome this problem we then decided to use FRUIT's formulae to simulate thermal sources in a radioactive environment. To put it simple, FRUIT (for Frascati Unfolding Interactive Tool) is an unfolding code for Bonner sphere spectrometers developed at the INFN-Frascati National Laboratory [32]. It basically do a fit neutron spectra by superposing up to four components (thermal, epithermal, fast and high energy neutrons) defined by seven positive parameters with a physical meaning. For our work, only the equations for the thermal and epithermal components were kept, and they can be found in **Table 3**, where $\phi(E)$ is the energy distribution in MeV^{-1} of the neutron fluence normalised to 1 cm^{-2} . In our table, $\phi_{\text{th}}(E)$ is the thermal Maxwellian component and $\phi_e(E)$ the epithermal one.

Thermal, $\phi_{\text{th}}(E)$, $E < 10^{-7} \text{ MeV}$	Epithermal, $\phi_e(E)$, $10^{-7} \text{ MeV} < E < 0.1 \text{ MeV}$
$\left(\frac{E}{T_o}\right) e^{(-E/T_o)}$	$[1 - e^{-(E/E_d)^2}] E^{(b-1)} e^{(-E/\beta')}$

Table 3: Expressions for the thermal components used to parameterise the neutron spectra in FRUIT

In the thermal equation, $T_o = 2.53 \times 10^{-8} \text{ MeV}$ represents the thermal component, i.e. the conventional thermal neutron energy. In the epithermal equation, the epithermal component $E_d = 7.07 \times 10^{-8} \text{ MeV}$ indicates the lower energy limit of the function. The parameters b and β' influence the slope of the rising or falling side of the curve, with $0.5 < b < 1.5$ and $0 < \beta' < 1$ (the 1.5 upper limit of b is here assumed, after running some tests, as there's a typo in FRUIT's paper stating that $0.5 < b < 0.5$ which doesn't make sense). Using these formulae, we can then visualise the spectra they will create in **Figure 10**. For the epithermals, b was taken around 1.0 with $\beta' = 0.01$ to recreate the epithermal "plateau" we were expecting. The energy limits here were not necessarily respected as our goal isn't to create a piece-wise function but to simulation each component separately and to sum them at the end.

(a) FRUIT's thermal neutrons spectrum (not limited to 10^{-7} MeV) (b) FRUIT's epithermal neutrons spectra for $b = 1.0, 1.02, 1.04$ and $\beta' = 0.01$

Figure 10: FRUIT's thermal and epithermal calculated energy spectra

The sources then implemented, the simulations can now be done. However a common problem we faced is the number of neutrons detected in the simulations. As we do a counting, a Poisson law can be used to calculate the uncertainty of our counting. Let's name n the minimum number of neutrons captured in a cube after a simulation. $u(n) = \sqrt{n}$ is its standard deviation and $\frac{u(n)}{n}$ is the relative uncertainty of our counting. Both our models are trained for a minimum number of $n = 1000$ neutrons captured per cubes to reduce the uncertainty of our counting down to $\frac{\sqrt{1000}}{1000} \approx 3\%$, but we realised that generating such data takes a good amount of time, principally for the DeepCompass model as we need to train the model over thousands of positions. For this reason, as we lacked of time to generate all the data, only a few numbers of sources will be kept for training on the 4 boxes system for the DeepCompass model.

5. Reconstruction of the direction of neutrons

The first model we focused on was the DeepCompass model for reconstruction of the direction of neutrons. Because of how difficult it is to spatially localise neutron radiations as explained before, we had to generate a good amount of data to train our models without generating too much as the Geant4 simulations and the conversion of the generated files in manipulable files consume a lot of time. For the 4-boxes system (4b system) we then decided to generate five sources, selected to represent different energy ranges, in 1,500 different random positions, all around the detector, with 5 million events. For the 2-boxes system (2b system), as around half of the particles were detected compared to the 4b system because of the cross-section, which also fasten the data generation, 3,000 different random positions were used but only with 1 million events each considering we decided to use here all the nine sources at our disposal, as it was the first time we were doing simulations with this system. Note that for the training, all the sources were randomly simulated at 1 to 8 m of the detector. For the testing, the positions were taken at 5 m of the detector. Using these data, the training dataset could then be created.

5.1 Dataset creation and predictions' visualisation

For our training datasets, we decided to create a dataframe of 5 columns:

1. A 64-dimensional vector column named "cubes", where the number at position i in the vector corresponds to the number of neutrons captured by the i -th cube.
2. Another 64-dimensional probability vector column named "input", which is a normalised fraction of counts of each cubes column's vector.
3. A 3-dimensional tuple column with the corresponding spherical coordinates of each position named "position".
4. A 3-dimensional tuple column with the calculated cartesian coordinates, corresponding to the direction vector, of each position named "target".
5. And a column with the name of the corresponding isotope for each source.

The data are then treated for training with a python script where we could change the number of hidden layers, the batchsize of each sample, the number of workers or of epochs, resume an old training and so on. The loss was calculated using PyTorch's MSE (Mean Squared Error) loss function of the neural network functional submodule (`torch.nn.functional`). It basically compute the mean squared error of each element and works very well with vectors in cartesian, which corresponds to the output given by our model.

To represent the model's predictions, we use a planisphere using a 4π map in Hammer projection. This projection was chosen for representation purposes because it is an equal-area projection which reduces the distortion in the regions of the outer meridians. The angular error calculation uses a geodesic which corresponds to the distance on a sphere between 2 points. It basically calculates the direct angle between the predicted cartesian direction vector and the real one. The advantage of a geodesic representation is that there's no bias at the poles. Compared to Earth geodesics for example,

the distance between two points here is numerically equal to the angle in radian since the radius is set to 1 m. Our geodesics are then created with both longitude and latitude, respectively corresponding to φ and θ in the spherical coordinates, to spatially localise each predicted position point around the detector. Their calculations were performed using the θ , φ nomenclature commonly used in physics. The equation of the geodesic calculation is the following:

$$s = r \times \cos^{-1}(\cos(\theta_1) \times \cos(\theta_2) + \sin(\theta_1) \times \sin(\theta_2) \times \cos(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2)) \quad (4)$$

A color bar is used to represent the angular error calculated with the geodesic. For the same representation purposes, the pixelation of the map was made using the HEALPix software. It stands for Hierarchical Equal Area isoLatitude Pixelation of a sphere, and produces a subdivision of a spherical surface where the same area is covered by each pixel as every other pixel. It was developed first to provide a suitable discretisation of functions on a sphere at high resolution for statistical and astrophysical analysis of massive full-sky datasets like full-sky maps of the microwave sky at an angular resolution of a few arcminutes from datasets produced by NASA's or ESA's observatory [33]. A good overview of what the geodesics look like with the detector positions can be seen on **Figure 11**. Note that the point located at latitude = 0° , longitude = 180° and the one located at latitude = 0° , longitude = -180° are the same and correspond to the back of the detector.

Figure 11: Comparison between a geodesic and the detector positions

5.2 Machine learning results: 4 boxes system

As said before, for the training of the 4 boxes system only 5 sources were kept: an $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source for its unique spectrum, with energies going from 0.1 MeV to 10 MeV, a ^{252}Cf spontaneous fission source, with energies going from 1 eV to 15 MeV, an $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ source, with energies going from 40 keV to 2 MeV, chosen for its low energy range, a PuO_2 source, with energies going from 2.2×10^{-3} eV to 25 MeV, and a ^{252}Cf spontaneous fission source thermalised by the environment using FRUIT's formulae.

Such a data generation already took several days, and yet the number of counts in the cubes for a single generation can go up to thousands of captured neutrons (can be 3000 or 8000 depending on the source and the position) and down to a hundred or a bit less for the cubes placed at the opposite position of the source. This problem causes then a statistical problem of class imbalance for our training, lowering the relative uncertainty down to 10% for the cubes with the fewest counts. Because of this problem, the calculated angular error in pointwise areas in our geodesics is uneven. In order to avoid that, mean geodesics were made by averaging every 2×2 block of the prediction array. Also to increase our number of generated data, a certain number of resampling was done on our dataframe. Let's say we do n resamples, our resampling will create $n - 1$ copies of our dataframe, apply each time a Poisson noise to the number of counts of each cube, by using their standard deviation, then recreate the input column by normalising the new data and concatenate the original dataframe with the $n-1$ copies as a single dataframe. Here, 30 resamples were made. A good example of a training result, with the ^{252}Cf , can be seen in **Figure 12** and **Figure 13** with a training loss epoch and validation loss comparison

in **Figure 14**. All the other geodesics can be seen in **Appendix B**.

Figure 12: Angular error of the predicted positions of the ^{252}Cf source

Figure 13: Angular error of the 2×2 mean predicted positions of the ^{252}Cf source

Figure 14: Training and validation loss comparison during the training of the model with the 4b system

After running some trainings, we also decided to train our model with a batchsize of 512, 1000 epochs, with four 128-neurons dense hidden layers. Obviously, the model used 64-dimension input layers corresponding to the counting of each cube and 3-dimension output layers corresponding to the predicted coordinates of the cartesian direction vectors. At the end a total of 58,244 parameters and 270,000 data was counted.

The geodesics in **Appendix B** shows us how efficient is the 4b system for neutron detection, especially for thermal and epithermal neutrons. There's indeed almost no angular error for the predicted positions of the thermalised ^{252}Cf source, and same goes for the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ source. Faster neutrons however, like the ones from the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source, show us that the model is more efficient when irradiated from the corners (see **Figure 11** for comparison). It can be explained by the cubic geometry of the system.

5.3 Finetuning using an AmBe source

To improve the performance of the model on real data, experimental data where measured using an AmBe source of 11.4 kHz of neutron activity. Multiple directions where acquired, first along the XY plane, with a step of 22.5° with $\theta = 90^\circ$ and the source placed at 1 m from the detector. To vary the environment, the positions of the detector and the source were swapped to take 12 other positions, along the same plane and with the same θ , with a 30° step. Using the pretrained model, a finetuning was done. For the training part, we first applied a Poisson noise to the number of counts in each cube for each position and used the real measured positions for the test. As expected, the results were more than satisfying and can be seen in **Figure 15**. Note that a 10° angular error from the experimental angle estimation of each position has to be considered. A measurement of the background was taken before and after the measurements, but subtracting it from the data didn't change much in the training.

Figure 15: First finetuning results

Then, to vary the value of θ , the source was placed on the ground at around $\theta = 144^\circ$ from the detector reference frame, e.g. when we took the positions at $\theta = 90^\circ$ the source was placed in front of the detector. A distance of 1.72m was calculated between the source and the center of the detector, but for the $\varphi = \pm 180^\circ$ position because of the wall, placed at like 1.704m. A measurement was taken every 45° . Afterwards, to change the measured value of θ again, the detector was turned, facing the ground, with the source still on the ground, to get approximately a $\theta = 54^\circ$ value. The same measurements were then taken with the same step. To challenge the model, the positions measured in the corner of the detector were not given in the training to see if the model could localise them by transfer learning. An angular error acceptance of 30° was taken just for this training. The result can be seen in **Figure 16**. The HEALPix pixelation was not kept here for visualisation. The result show us that the model can't really predict these unseen positions. Although, some of them seem better predicted than others, after running multiple trainings we realised these better predicted positions were not always the same, making us think it is quite random. Both trainings and validation loss comparisons can be found in **Appendix C**.

Figure 16: Final finetuning results by transfer learning

5.4 Machine learning results: 2 boxes system

With the geometry modifications, training data could finally be generated for a system with only two boxes. As said before, all the nine sources in our disposal were simulated, i.e. the ^{252}Cf , D_2O -moderated ^{252}Cf , $^{241}\text{AmBe}$, ^{241}AmB , $^{241}\text{AmLi}$, PuBe , ^{238}U , PuO_2 and PuMetal source. The same parameters were used for the training than the 4b system for the same reasons, besides the input layer being obviously reduced to 32 for this system. A total of 54,148 parameters and 810,000 data was counted.

Because of the loss in both moderators and lithium screens, a non-negligible loss in captured neutrons has to be noted. For the lowest energy source, the AmLi , the number of captured neutron can go down to a hundred, giving again a relative uncertainty of 10%. But for the source with which the model struggles the most with, i.e. the AmBe , the number of captured neutrons can go down to around 35 and up to around 455, giving a relative uncertainty going from 4.7% to 17%, which is quite high. For the same reasons as for the 4b system, a 2×2 mean of the angular error was made to smooth the representations. A good example of the training results can be seen in **Figure 17** and in **Figure 18**, with the evolution of the validation and training loss in **Figure 19**. All the other geodesics obtained after training for this system can be seen in **Appendix D**. Contrary to the 4b system, the 2b system seems to be more efficient for fast neutrons at $\theta = 90^\circ$ (latitude = 0°), so parallel to the lithium screens, and eventually at the $\theta = 0^\circ$ pole (latitude = 90°), but seems way less efficient for really fast neutron sources. This can be explained by the quantity of moderators: as they were halved, fast neutrons cannot be thermalised as efficiently than with the 4b system. As shown by the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ predicted positions, the system seems to struggle even for thermal neutrons if they're coming following the z axis, but is pretty efficient otherwise. In practical cases, as most of the sources will be thermalised by the hydrogens present in the surrounding environment, even more if there's water, the system will probably turn out to be quite efficient anyway.

Figure 17: Angular error of the predicted positions of the ^{252}Cf source

Figure 18: Angular error of the 2×2 mean predicted positions of the ^{252}Cf source

Figure 19: Training and validation loss comparison during the training of the model with the 2b system

Because of these newly discovered properties, a 2b system can then be imagined to be used by hand, while a 4b system, heavier, can be imagined to be used as a turret. As a box only weighs 1.7 kg, a 3 kg detector is conceivable. The future arrangements of the detector are still in reflection.

To conclude on this part, the 4b system has proven itself capable of detecting the direction of the neutrons emitted from different sources down to angular errors below 5%. In order to localise a source in the field, multiple measurements have to be taken to perform a triangulation which is supposed to provide the position of the source. Using results from Sebastián Valladares and Sajid Saleem [34] internship report on the subject, predictions with angular errors below 5% are needed to perform a good triangulation. Further work on this subject is still to be done. Concerning the 2b system, the results are satisfactory to consider the construction of a lighter model, though it has its limits.

6. Fluence reconstruction for dose estimation

6.1 Data generation

For the dose estimation, the sources for the simulation are composed of elementary bricks:

1. A fast component, representing neutrons coming from the sources.
2. A directional epithermal component to represent fast neutrons from the sources after one or more scatterings.
3. A thermal isotropic sphere, corresponding to neutrons moderated by the environment.
4. And finally a part simulating thermal neutrons scattering back inside the detector.

Figure 20: Schematic of possible components for training data composition, adapted from Nicholas Reed thesis [19]

Each of these elements were simulated such that we can compose, with different fractions, a fluence. For the fast components and the epithermal ones coming with them, we also generated points that can vary in space, located in three concentric circles at 15° , 30° and 45° of the central position, forming a cone, to teach the model that the source can be shifted. For the first two circles, out of the six wanted positions only three of them were generated to reduce the generation time by using the symmetry of the system following the z -axis. For the third one, as it is bigger, eight positions were considered and four were generated. The calculation of the positions can be seen in **Appendix E**. The positions in circle 2 being the same as in circle 1 but for 30° , it was not represented here. Note that for the epithermal part, the same parameters as in **Figure 10b** were used.

The model is then supposed to be able to predict a source fluence with these components. As only a few positions are necessary to train this model, enough events were generated to reach the needed 1000 minimal number of captured neutrons in each cube to get the wanted relative efficiency of 3%.

6.2 Fluence reconstruction results

Using the generated data, a dataset was created and fluence reconstruction trainings were performed. The participation of each source component was estimated by calculating their fraction in the fluence, and the given ratio of each component can be modified. Two types of training were then made to challenge the model: one with a significant thermal and epithermal ratio for each source and another one with only their fast component and a bit of backscattering. The ambient dose equivalent, defined by ICRP-74, is also calculated alongside the fluence reconstruction using the conversion coefficients, but as the tested ratios aren't always realistic their value isn't either. Results for the AmBe source can be seen in **Figure 21**, and for the other sources in **Appendix F**. It is easy to see that the system struggles more when only the fast component is present, particularly, it always expect the presence of a thermal and an epithermal component. In the case of the ^{252}Cf source, the model tends to mix it up with the AmBe source as they're quite similar when captured. A comparison of the normalized number of neutron captured by cubes of the two sources, showing their similarity for the system, can be found in **Appendix G**. This can be easily explained by the fact the composition of a target is biased with thermal neutrons, and that the system was never trained with a pure fast neutron source.

Even if further trainings are still required, by trying different ratios for example, the nFluence model proved itself quite efficient for fluence reconstruction with a slight, but negligible, bias towards thermal neutrons. Its performance allows the system to realise a good estimation of the dose.

(a) Fluence AmBe, thermal components ratio prevailing

(b) Fluence AmBe, fast component ratio prevailing

Figure 21: Reconstruction of the composition of the neutron fluence of the AmBe source. Ratio FEST gives here the ratio respectively used for the Fast, Epithermal, (Back)Scattering and Thermal components. Dose P/T delivers a comparison between the calculated ambient dose equivalent of the given fluence (target) and the predicted fluence (prediction).

7. Conclusion

The present work investigated the performance of the directional prediction model of the new nFacet system and proved its performance, with angular errors going down 5% for most of the sources. In the field, a source could then be localised using triangulation with multiple measurements. An enhanced performance has to be noted on the corners due to the cubic geometry.

Considering the finetuning results, the system has proven to be able to detect sources at given position in the field, though it struggles with transfer learning when given positions never seen before.

The simulations performed on the newly tested 2 boxes system suggest that a lighter version of the detector is conceivable, as it is nearly as efficient than the 4 boxes system for thermal neutron detection and has proven to perform well on the sides for some faster neutron sources. However, at the present time, more generated data are needed for these simulations to reach an acceptable relative uncertainty, even for the 4 boxes system.

After generating their data, the training results of the nFluence model also show the efficiency of the system for fluence reconstruction, and then dose estimation. Although a certain bias on the thermal components have to be noted, leaving room for improvement. In order to differentiate similar sources, like the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ and the ^{252}Cf , more data could also be generated to reach a relative uncertainty of 1%.

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A. Overview of the geometries used to calculate fluence-to-dose conversion coefficients

Figure 22: Schematic of geometries used to calculate fluence-to-dose conversion coefficients, adapted from Nicholas Reed thesis [19]

B. 4 boxes system angular error of the positions predicted by the DeepCompass model for 4 different sources

B.1 ^{252}Cf thermalised using FRUIT's formulae

Figure 23: Angular error of the predicted positions of the thermalised ^{252}Cf source

Figure 24: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the thermalised ^{252}Cf source

B.2 $^{241}\text{AmLi}$

Figure 25: Angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ source

Figure 26: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ source

B.3 PuO₂

Figure 27: Angular error of the predicted positions of the PuO₂ source

Figure 28: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the PuO₂ source

B.4 $^{241}\text{AmBe}$

Figure 29: Angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source

Figure 30: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source

C. Losses comparisons of the finetuning trainings

Training and validation loss comparison of the finetuning with the AmBe source

Figure 31: Training and validation loss comparison with the AmBe first positions

Training and validation loss comparison, finetuning, AmBe source, new positions

Figure 32: Training and validation loss comparison with the AmBe second positions and transfer learning attempt

D. 2 boxes system angular error of the positions predicted by the DeepCompass model for 8 different sources

D.1 $^{241}\text{AmLi}$

Figure 33: Angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ source

Figure 34: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$ source

D.2 ^{238}U

Figure 35: Angular error of the predicted positions of the ^{238}U source

Figure 36: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the ^{238}U source

D.3 D₂O-moderated ²⁵²Cf

Figure 37: Angular error of the predicted positions of the D₂O-moderated ²⁵²Cf source

Figure 38: 2 × 2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the D₂O-moderated ²⁵²Cf source

D.4 PuO₂

Figure 39: Angular error of the predicted positions of the PuO₂ source

Figure 40: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the PuO₂ source

D.5 PuMetal

Figure 41: Angular error of the predicted positions of the PuMetal source

Figure 42: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the PuMetal source

D.6 PuBe

Figure 43: Angular error of the predicted positions of the PuBe source

Figure 44: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the PuBe source

D.7 ^{241}AmB

Figure 45: Angular error of the predicted positions of the ^{241}AmB source

Figure 46: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the ^{241}AmB source

D.8 $^{241}\text{AmBe}$

Figure 47: Angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source

Figure 48: 2×2 mean angular error of the predicted positions of the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source

E. Calculation of the cone positions for dose estimation

Figure 49: Calculated additional positions for the 15° circle (same equations for the 30° circle)

Figure 50: Calculated additional positions for the 45° circle

F. Fluence reconstruction of 7 different sources

F.1 ^{252}Cf

Figure 51: Fluence reconstruction of the ^{252}Cf , thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 52: Fluence reconstruction of the ^{252}Cf , fast component ratio prevailing

F.2 $^{241}\text{AmLi}$

Figure 53: Fluence reconstruction of the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$, thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 54: Fluence reconstruction of the $^{241}\text{AmLi}$, fast component ratio prevailing

F.3 ^{241}AmB

Figure 55: Fluence reconstruction of the ^{241}AmB , thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 56: Fluence reconstruction of the ^{241}AmB , fast component ratio prevailing

F.4 ^{238}U

Figure 57: Fluence reconstruction of the ^{238}U , thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 58: Fluence reconstruction of the ^{238}U , fast component ratio prevailing

F.5 PuBe

Figure 59: Fluence reconstruction of the PuBe, thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 60: Fluence reconstruction of the PuBe, fast component ratio prevailing

F.6 PuO₂

Figure 61: Fluence reconstruction of the PuO₂, thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 62: Fluence reconstruction of the PuO₂, fast component ratio prevailing

F.7 PuMetal

Figure 63: Fluence reconstruction of the PuMetal, thermal components ratio prevailing

Figure 64: Fluence reconstruction of the PuMetal, fast component ratio prevailing

G. Neutron capture similarity of the ^{252}Cf and $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ sources

Figure 65: Comparison of the normalized number of neutrons captured by cubes at position ($r=1$, $\theta=1.571$, $\varphi=0$) for both ^{252}Cf and $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ sources